

STUDY OF THE MORPHOLOGY OF SYNTHESIZED BORON NITRIDE NANOPARTICLES WITH HEXAGONAL CRYSTAL STRUCTURE

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In this work, we conducted a study on the production of boron nitride nanoparticles with a hexagonal crystal structure (h-BN). To synthesize boron nitride nanoparticles, we used widely available reagents such as boric acid and urea as starting materials. The starting substances - boric acid and urea - are dissolved in different proportions in water; then, the solution is dehydrated and crushed. Next, a two-stage heat treatment is carried out. In the first stage, the resulting crystals are heated to 600°C for 3 hours in a muffle furnace under a nitrogen atmosphere. Following this, a second stage of heat treatment is conducted at a temperature of 1000°C in an atmosphere of hydrogen and nitrogen. The resulting powder is washed with deionized water and then rinsed with ethanol to remove water. Finally, the product is dried at 60°C for 12 hours.

The shape and size of the synthesized boron nitride nanoparticles were studied using a transmission electron microscope (Figure 1a). The size distribution of BN nanoparticles is shown in Figure 1b.

Picture 1 - (a) TEM image of BN nanoparticles; b – size distribution of nanoparticles.

It was found that the resulting h-BN nanopowders have a spherical shape and a narrow particle size distribution (Figure 1a). The size of the resulting nanoparticles ranges from 2 to 10 nm, with an average particle size of 6 nm (Figure 2a).

The presented method has several advantages over traditional production methods. Specifically, it utilizes widely available starting materials such as urea and boric acid. The use of a two-stage heat treatment enables the production of nanoparticles with a narrow granulometric composition. Additionally, this synthesis employs relatively low temperatures, and the use of nitrogen and hydrogen gases in the atmosphere is relatively non-toxic, unlike the traditionally used ammonia in CVD synthesis.